

How do researchers choose their goals of inference? A survey experiment on the effects of the state of research and method preferences on the choice between research goals

Appendix

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A1: Sample selection and descriptive statistics

For the following descriptive statistics, we report results that are based on the final sample of 901 participants used in the main analysis, i.e., respondents who completed the survey, passed the attention check question and had method preferences applicable to our study.

Table A1 reports the country of residence of respondents, i.e., if they are employed at a university located in the respective country. The share of respondents from Europe and the US is about equal (i.e., 466 US and 435 European respondents). The respondents from European countries are mostly located in the UK and Germany, who, combined, account for about half of the European sample.

Table A1: Country coverage

	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
BE	6	0.67	0.67
CH	64	7.10	7.77
DE	96	10.65	18.42
DK	45	4.99	23.42
FI	2	0.22	23.64
IT	19	2.11	25.75
NL	34	3.77	29.52
NO	13	1.44	30.97
SE	29	3.22	34.18
UK	127	14.10	48.28
USA	466	51.72	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

In Table A2, we show the response rates for our survey invitations across countries.

Table A2: Response rates

Country	Invitations	Completed	Response rate
BE	164	10	6.10%
CH	357	71	19.89%
DE	601	108	17.97%
DK	261	48	18.39%
FI	47	3	6.38%
IT	57	22	38.60%
NL	349	37	10.60%
NO	79	15	18.99%
SE	309	29	9.39%
UK	1691	161	9.52%
US	3316	543	16.38%

Table A3 lists all universities that were included in the sample.

Table A3: List of European and US Universities

European	US
Aarhus University	Boston University
Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg	Brown University
Durham University	Carnegie Mellon University
ETH Zurich	Columbia University
Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	Cornell University
Freie Universität Berlin	Duke University
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	Harvard University
KU Leuven	John Hopkins University
King's College London	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Leiden University	New York University
London School of Economics	Northwestern University
Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	Princeton University
Lund University	Stanford University
Maastricht University	The University of Chicago
Queen Mary University of London	University of California, Berkley
RWTH Aachen	University of California, Davis
Technische Universität München	University of California, Los Angeles
University College London	University of California, San Diego
University of Amsterdam	University of California, Santa Barbara
University of Bern	University of Illinois at Urbana-Cham..
University of Bonn	University of Michigan
University of Cambridge	University of Minnesota
University of Edinburgh	University of North Carolina at Chape..
University of Glasgow	University of Pennsylvania
University of Groningen	University of Southern California
University of Göttingen	University of Texas at Austin
University of Manchester	University of Washington
University of Oxford	University of Wisconsin
University of Sheffield	Washington University in St. Louis
University of St Andrews	Yale University
University of Warwick	
Universität Basel	
Universität Heidelberg	
Universität Mannheim	
Universität Zürich	
Uppsala University	

Since no comprehensive population data for political scientists are available, we constructed a sampling frame based on the Times Higher Education (THE) World University Ranking 2018. We

selected the top 30 universities in Europe and the USA that have a political science department and compiled an address database that contains the scientific staff of these departments.¹

Guest lecturers, associates, research and teaching assistants, and university administration were excluded from the target population. We considered the following chairs, institutes, and departments to be relevant to the academic discipline of political science:

1. Chairs, institutes, or departments with “politics”, “political science”, “democracy”, and “governance” in the title.
2. Chairs, institutes, or departments of international relations
3. Chairs, institutes, or departments of European politics (e.g., European Institute).

Table A4 reports summary statistics for the self-reported age of the respondents.² On average, participants are 35 years old. The distribution of age indicates that the sample is dominated by younger researchers.

Table A4: Distribution of age

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Age	901	35.024	9.396	22	78

Table A5 describes the distribution of the self-reported gender of respondents. The results show an unbalanced distribution of male and female scholars, with the latter accounting for only about one-third of the sample.

Table A5: Distribution of gender

Gender	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Female	292	32.41	32.41
Male	579	64.26	96.67
Prefer not to answer	30	3.33	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

Table A6 shows the distribution of professional status in our sample. For this question, participants had to select one of the following options: Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, Full Professor, Graduate Student, Postdoc, Undergraduate Student, or Other. A total of 54 “Other”

¹ We increased the number of European universities included in the sample to 36 to achieve the desired sample size.

² For the question about their age, seven respondents gave unrealistic answers (i.e., below 18 or above 100). We used mean imputation to replace these values.

answers were classified by the authors of this study. These answers mostly refer to scholars who belong to the category “Graduate Student” but, for example, consider themselves to be a “PhD Student”. Moreover, some participants described themselves as Lecturer or Fellow, which we considered to be similar to Postdoc. In the preanalysis plan, we specified only three categories for academic status (PhD, postdoc/assistant professor or full professor). We therefore opted for the following categorizations for the analysis:

1. Professor, including the categories “Full Professor” and “Associate Professor”
2. Senior Scholar, including the categories “Assistant Professor”, “Postdoc” and related lecturer positions with a completed PhD
3. Junior Scholar, including the category “Graduate Student”

A few participants indicated that they were an “Undergraduate Student”. We excluded these respondents from the analysis because they are not actively conducting empirical research at this stage of their career and have most likely not yet received extensive methods training. For participants who answered that they recently left academia, we coded their status as the last position that they occupied.

Table A6: Distribution of professional status

	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Professor	202	22.42	22.42
Senior Scholar	286	31.74	54.16
Junior Scholar	413	45.84	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

We evaluate the demographics of US component of the sample by comparing them with a membership survey from the American Political Science Association (APSA) conducted in December 2017 (APSA, 2019).³ The distribution of gender in our survey closely matches the data collected by APSA. 64.08% of the APSA members reported being male and 35.89% female (APSA, 2019). Among the US respondents in our sample, 61.59 % report their gender as male, 35.62 % female, and 2.79 % prefer not to answer this question. To match the format of measuring

³ The APSA data is not a random sample of the profession itself, but neither can this be claimed for our sample because we sampled from top-30 THE universities. The APSA data were the most comprehensive in terms of demographic information that was available for comparison.

the age of respondents in the APSA member survey, we recoded our data into seven age groups. Table A7 shows the percentage share of age groups for APSA members and our sample.

Table A7: Comparison of age groups

Age group	Survey sample	APSA members
<25	4%	2.41%
25-34	56.27%	27.65%
35-44	25.75%	27.41%
45-54	8.88%	18.97%
55-64	3.33%	11.64%
65-74	1.44%	8.68%
>75	0.33%	3.23%

Table A7 shows that more than half of the participants of our survey are between 25 and 34 years old. For APSA members, only about 27% fall into this category. Thus, in comparison to the APSA members, our sample is more skewed towards younger scholars.⁴

We report the distribution of method preferences among participants of the survey in Table A8.

Table A8: Method preferences

	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Small N	160	17.76	17.76
Large N	341	37.85	55.60
Mixed-method	400	44.40	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

For this categorization, participants had to select one or more of following options: Statistical Analysis, QCA, Process Tracing, Interpretivist Qualitative Methods, Experiments, or Other. As described in the preanalysis plan, we categorized respondents as follows. Qualitative researchers are defined as using the following methods in empirical analysis: Interpretivist Qualitative Methods, process tracing, and/or QCA. Quantitative researchers are defined as using the following methods in empirical analysis: statistical analysis, and/or experiments. Mixed-method researchers are defined as all respondents that combine qualitative and quantitative research methods as described above. Moreover, 180 respondents indicated that they use “Other” methods in an open-ended question. To categorize these answers, we applied the following coding rules:

⁴ We obtain a substantially similar distribution of age groups if we only look at the US scholars in our sample.

1. Qualitative Methods: All answers that explicitly refer to qualitative methods or the use of case studies, or any other description of interpretivist methods, process tracing, and/or QCA.
2. Quantitative Methods: All answers that explicitly refer to statistics, quantitative or computational methods or any other description of statistical analysis, and/or experiments
3. Mixed-Method: All answers indicating the explicit use of mixed-method research or a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods as defined above.

Table A9 describes the distribution of the self-reported assessment of the number of cases that participants usually study in empirical analysis. Respondents answered the question, “In your empirical research, how many cases do you usually analyze?”.

Table A9: Number of cases

	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Small N	213	23.64	23.64
Large N	454	50.39	74.03
Mixed-method	210	23.31	97.34
Not applicable	24	2.66	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

This was an open-ended question that allowed both numerical and non-numerical responses, providing respondents with the opportunity to give a broader description of their preferences (e.g., “I conduct single-case studies and large-N analysis with more than 1000 observations”). To group these answers, we applied the following coding rules:

1. Small N: All answers indicating the use of 1 to 50 cases
2. Large N: All answers indicating the use of more than 50 cases
3. Mixed-Method: All answers indicating the use of small and large samples as defined above

Using the data on preferences for methods and number of cases described above, we categorize participants as qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-method researchers. Qualitative researchers are defined as using a small number of cases and the following methods in empirical analysis: interpretivist methods, process tracing, and/or QCA. Quantitative researchers are defined as using a large number of cases and the following methods in empirical analysis: statistical analysis, and/or

experiments. Mixed-method researchers are defined as all respondents that combine small and large samples and/or different research methods. Table A10 describes the distribution of these research method preferences in our sample.

Table A10: Research method preferences

	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Qualitative	150	16.65	16.65
Quantitative	309	34.30	50.94
Mixed-method	442	49.06	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

Almost half of the sample can be categorized as mixed-method researchers. Pure quantitative scholars account for more than one third of the sample and pure qualitative scholars comprise only 17% of the sample.

Table A11 describes the distribution of our outcome measure of goals of inference. Regardless of the experimental manipulation, most respondents chose to conduct an exploratory study, which accounted for almost half of the sample. Confirmatory and process-oriented study were chosen at a much lower rate, with a share of 24.5% and 28.6% respectively.

Table A11: Distribution of goals of inference

	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Exploratory	422	46.84	46.84
Confirmatory	221	24.53	71.37
Process	258	28.63	100.00
Total	901	100.00	

Figure A1 presents the vignette that was used for the experiment.

Figure A1: Experimentally manipulated vignettes

Vignette version 1

Imagine you want to conduct research on a political phenomenon that has already been extensively studied. For decades, many scholars collected data on this topic and proposed and analyzed many different hypotheses to explain it.

Vignette version 2

Imagine you want to conduct research on a political phenomenon that so far has not been extensively studied. Only recently have some scholars begun to collect data on this topic and few hypotheses have been proposed and tested to explain it.

Table A12 describes the results of a randomization check, which tests if respondents who received the experimental treatment significantly differed from respondents that did not receive the treatment on number of covariates. There appear to be no statistically significant differences with regard to age, gender, professional status, method preferences, and the continent of respondents.

Table A12: Randomization checks

Factor	extensively studied	not extensively studied	p- value
N	459	442	
Age, mean (SD)	34.68 (9.31)	35.39 (9.48)	0.26
Gender, freq. (%)			0.60
Female	147 (32.0%)	145 (32.8%)	
Male	294 (64.1%)	285 (64.5%)	
Prefer not to answer	18 (3.9%)	12 (2.7%)	
Status, freq. (%)			0.29
Professor	93 (20.3%)	109 (24.7%)	
Senior Scholar	150 (32.7%)	136 (30.8%)	
Junior Scholar	216 (47.1%)	197 (44.6%)	
Method preference, freq. (%)			0.40
Qualitative	70 (15.3%)	80 (18.1%)	
Quantitative	165 (35.9%)	144 (32.6%)	
Mixed-method	224 (48.8%)	218 (49.3%)	
Continent, freq. (%)			0.73
Europe	219 (47.7%)	216 (48.9%)	
US	240 (52.3%)	226 (51.1%)	

A.2: Detailed regression results

In this section, we report the complete results in tabular form for the three base outcomes.

Table A13: Multinomial logit models with base outcome *exploratory*

	Confirmatory	Process
Not extensively studied	-2.29* (0.16)	-2.56* (0.34)
Quantitative	1.64* (0.36)	-0.41 (0.28)
Mixed-method	1.22* (0.32)	-0.03 (0.26)
Male	0.31 (0.20)	0.02 (0.14)
Prefer not to answer	0.16 (0.49)	0.18 (0.57)
Senior Scholar	0.22 (0.62)	0.54 (0.63)
Junior Scholar	-0.22 (0.89)	0.59 (0.75)
Age	-0.01 (0.03)	0.02 (0.02)
US	-0.20 (0.18)	-0.38* (0.14)
Constant	-0.48 (1.63)	-0.04 (1.53)
Observations	901	

*Robust standard errors clustered by country in parentheses, * $p < 0.05$*

Table A14: Multinomial logit models with base outcome *confirmatory*

	Exploratory	Process
Not extensively studied	2.29* (0.16)	-0.28 (0.29)
Quantitative	-1.64* (0.36)	-2.05* (0.40)
Mixed-method	-1.22* (0.32)	-1.25* (0.40)
Male	-0.31 (0.20)	-0.28 (0.23)
Prefer not to answer	-0.16 (0.49)	0.02 (0.37)
Senior Scholar	-0.22 (0.62)	0.32 (0.36)
Junior Scholar	0.22 (0.89)	0.82 (0.59)
Age	0.01 (0.03)	0.03 (0.02)
US	0.20 (0.18)	-0.18 (0.13)
Constant	0.48 (1.63)	0.44 (1.25)
Observations	901	

*Robust standard errors clustered by country in parentheses, * p < 0.05*

Table A15: Multinomial logit models with base outcome *process*

	Exploratory	Confirmatory
Not extensively studied	2.56* (0.34)	0.28 (0.29)
Quantitative	0.41 (0.28)	2.05* (0.40)
Mixed-method	0.03 (0.26)	1.25* (0.40)
Male	-0.02 (0.14)	0.28 (0.23)
Prefer not to answer	-0.18 (0.57)	-0.02 (0.37)
Senior Scholar	-0.54 (0.63)	-0.32 (0.36)
Junior Scholar	-0.59 (0.75)	-0.82 (0.59)
Age	-0.02 (0.02)	-0.03 (0.02)
US	0.38* (0.14)	0.18 (0.13)
Constant	0.04 (1.53)	-0.44 (1.25)
Observations	901	

*Robust standard errors clustered by country in parentheses, * $p < 0.05$*

A.3: Interaction effects

In this section, we discuss the interaction effects reported in the main text in greater detail. Figure A2 provides detailed results about the effect of the experimental treatment across research cultures.

Figure A2: Effect of experimental treatment across research cultures

The estimates show that the change in the probability of choosing a specific goal of inference is induced by being confronted with an understudied research topic. Across research cultures, the effect estimates for all three goals of inference point in the same direction. Regardless of the method preference of scholars, the experimental treatment increases the probability of choosing an exploratory design and decreases the probability of choosing a confirmatory or process-oriented design respectively.

With regard to the choice of an exploratory research design, the treatment effects are similar in size across research cultures. Being confronted with an understudied research topic increases the probability of choosing an exploratory goal of inference by 53% for qualitative researchers, by 50% for quantitative researchers, and by 56% for mixed-methods researchers. As indicated by the clearly overlapping confidence intervals, differences in treatment effects across research cultures

are not statistically significant.⁵ With regard to the choice of a confirmatory research design, our results show a negative treatment effect across all three research cultures, indicating that, given an understudied research topic, this goal of inference is less likely to be chosen. The estimates of the size of the treatment effect differ across research cultures. For qualitative scholars, the point estimates indicate a decrease of 12%, for quantitative researcher 24%, and for mixed-methods researchers 23%.⁶ However, confidence intervals overlap considerably, indicating that differences are not statistically significant. Finally, with regard to the choice of a process-oriented research design, our results indicate that the treatment effect is negative across all three research cultures. Again, there are substantial differences with regard to the size of the treatment effect, which is estimated as a reduction of 41% for qualitative researchers, 26% for quantitative researchers, and 33% for mixed-methods researchers. However, once again, confidence intervals show a considerable overlap and thus, there are no statistically significant differences of the treatment effect across research cultures.

Figure A3 reports the probability of choosing a specific goal of inference across method preferences and treatment conditions. This allows us to determine whether qualitative, quantitative and mixed-methods researchers choose a different goal of inference *conditional upon* being confronted with the same state of knowledge. Figure A3 shows that for an understudied research topic, scholars across all three research cultures are most likely to choose an exploratory research design. Point estimates indicate a probability of almost 80% for qualitative researchers, 71% for quantitative researchers, and 75% for mixed-methods researchers respectively. Confidence intervals overlap clearly, indicating that differences across groups are not statistically significant.

However, with regard to the probability of choosing a confirmatory research design, there appear to be substantial and significant differences across research cultures when being confronted with

⁵ We know that two confidence intervals for effect estimates can overlap, indicating non-significance, while the confidence interval for the difference in effect estimates as the relevant quantity of interest does not include 0 and suggests statistical significance. We do not report confidence intervals for differences in effect estimates because this can only occur at the margin, whereas the confidence intervals that we present here always clearly and strongly overlap.

⁶ The treatment effect for qualitative researchers is not statistically significant at conventional levels ($p = 0.062$).

an understudied research topic. Under this condition, the probability of choosing a confirmatory research design is estimated as 2% for qualitative researchers, 22% for quantitative researchers, and 11% for mixed-method researchers respectively. These differences across research cultures are statistically significant and also substantially important.

Figure A3: Probability of choosing a specific goal of inference across research cultures and treatment conditions⁷

For the probability of choosing a process-oriented goal of inference, we find substantial and significant differences between qualitative and quantitative researchers confronted with an understudied research topic. The lower panel of Figure A3 shows that point estimates are projected to be 18% for qualitative researchers, 7% for quantitative researchers, and 14% for mixed-method

⁷ The lower bound of the confidence interval for qualitative scholars who received the treatment of an understudied research topic in the middle panel of Figure A3 is below zero; this panel refers to the probability of choosing a confirmatory research design. This is caused by the delta-method utilized to compute standard errors for marginal effects calculations, which relies on a normal sampling distribution that can take values from -infinity to +infinity. The replication code contains an alternative procedure to compute Figure A3, which applies a logit transformation to compute the limits of confidence intervals, i.e., confidence intervals are supposed to lie between 0 and 1. However, this alternative procedure produces substantially similar results to those reported here with regard to the estimated treatment effects and their interaction.

researchers respectively. The difference between qualitative and quantitative researchers is statistically significant and substantially important.

These results highlight that while most scholars, regardless of their method preferences, opt for an exploratory goal of inference if the state of research is understudied, substantial differences between qualitative and quantitative scholars exists among those that deviate from the majority choice. Here, qualitative researchers prefer a process-oriented design and quantitative scholars opt for a confirmatory design. Results for mixed-method researchers in this regard are mostly inconclusive.

Looking at the treatment condition of a saturated state of knowledge, we find substantial variation in the preference of scholars with different research cultures. In line with the main effect of the experimental treatment, only a small percentage of researchers prefer to conduct an exploratory study under these conditions. There appears to be no relevant difference across research cultures with regard to choosing an exploratory goal of inference. Point estimates are 27% for qualitative researchers, 21% for quantitative researchers, and 19% for mixed-methods researchers respectively. Confidence intervals are large, especially for qualitative researchers, which is due to the small size of these subgroups. Confidence intervals also overlap widely, indicating that differences in point estimates between these groups are not statistically significant.

However, when comparing the probability of choosing a confirmatory goal of inferences within the treatment condition of an extensively studied research topic, relevant differences exist across research cultures. Point estimates are 14% for qualitative researchers, 46% for quantitative researchers, and 34% for mixed-method researchers respectively. These differences are statistically significant and substantially important for comparisons across all three groups.⁸

Finally, there are relevant differences between researchers with different method preferences with regard to the probability of choosing a process-oriented goal of inference under conditions of a saturated research topic. Here, point estimates are 59% for qualitative researchers, 33% for quantitative researchers, and 47% for mixed-method researchers respectively. Again, these differences are statistically significant and substantially important.

⁸ A Wald-test of first order differences indicates that the difference between mixed-methods and quantitative researchers is also statistically significant.

In sum, these results for the treatment by research culture interaction indicate that, while scholars across all three research cultures largely prefer an exploratory study given an understudied research topic, differences exist for those who deviate from the majority choice, with qualitative researchers being more likely to prefer a process-oriented study over a confirmatory study and, vice versa, quantitative scholars preferring a confirmatory study over a process-oriented research design. Results for mixed-method researchers are inconclusive in this regard. Moreover, the findings reveal that substantial differences exist across research cultures with regard to the choice of goals of inference when being confronted with a research topic that already has been extensively studied. Under this condition, qualitative and mixed-method researchers are most likely to choose a process-oriented design, while quantitative researchers prefer a confirmatory design.

Next, we evaluate whether scholars in the EU and the US respond differently to the experimental treatment and if, within each treatment condition (understudied vs. saturated state of research), researchers from the EU and the US chose different goals of inference. First, Figure A4 reports the treatment effect of an understudied research topic for each goal of inference across continents.

Figure A4: Effect of experimental treatment across continents

With regard to the choice of an exploratory research design, the point estimates for EU and US scholars are both positive and large, which means that the treatment substantially increases the choice of this design for scholars of both continents.

Being confronted with an understudied research topic increases the probability of choosing an exploratory goal of inference relative to a saturated state of knowledge by 59% for EU scholars and 47% for US scholars. The difference in the size of the treatment effect is larger for EU scholars and this difference in effect size is also statistically significant. With regard to the choice of a confirmatory research design, our results indicate a negative treatment effect for scholars of both continents, demonstrating that, given an understudied research topic, this goal of inference is less likely to be chosen. The estimates of the treatment effect differ only slightly, with a 20% reduction for EU scholars and a 23% reduction for US scholars. The difference of about 3% in the size of the treatment effects between EU and US scholars is not statistically significant. Finally, with regard to the choice of a process-oriented research design, our results indicate that the treatment effect is negative for scholars of both continents. However, there are substantial differences with regard to the size of the treatment effect, which is estimated as a reduction of 39% for EU researchers and 24% for US scholars. The substantial difference in the size of the treatment effects is also statistically significant.

Second, Figure A4 reports the probability of choosing a specific goal of inference across treatment conditions and continents. Given an understudied research topic, scholars in the EU and the US are most likely to choose an exploratory goal of inference. Under this condition, our estimates indicate that EU and US scholars chose an exploratory research topic with a probability of 75% and 74% respectively. Here, differences between EU and US scholars are neither substantial nor statistically significant.

With regard to the probability of choosing a confirmatory or process-oriented research design, there also appears to be no relevant differences between EU and US scholars under conditions of an understudied research topic. For a confirmatory research design, the estimated probabilities are 14% for EU scholars and 12% for US scholars under conditions of an understudied research topic.

For process-oriented research designs, the point estimates indicate a probability of 11% for EU scholars and 14% for US scholars under conditions of an understudied research topic.⁹

However, for the treatment condition of a saturated state of knowledge, we find more substantial differences between EU and US scholars in choosing among goals of inference. As shown in the upper-panel of Figure A5, EU scholars are substantially less likely than US scholars to choose an exploratory research design under conditions of a saturated state of knowledge. Point estimates indicate a probability of 15% for EU and 26% for US scholars; this difference is also statistically significant. The middle-panel of Figure A5 shows that there seem to be no substantial differences between EU and US scholars with regard to the choice of a confirmatory research design under conditions of an extensively studied research topic. Here, point estimates are 35% for EU and 36% for US scholars, and this difference is not statistically significant.

Figure A5: Probability of choosing a specific goal of inference across continents and treatment conditions

⁹ A Wald-test of first order differences indicates that the small difference between EU and US researchers regarding the probability of choosing a process-oriented research design under conditions of an understudied research topic is statistically significant.

The lower-panel of Figure A5 shows that EU scholars are substantially more likely than US scholars to choose a process-oriented research design under conditions of a saturated state of knowledge. Point estimates indicate a probability of 50% for EU and 38% for US scholars. This difference is substantially important and statistically significant.

In sum, the analysis of the interaction between the experimental treatment and the continent where scholars are based suggests two important patterns. First, the experimental treatment of an understudied research topic has a stronger effect on EU relative to US scholars with regard to the choice of an exploratory design and process-oriented design. Second, under the condition of a saturated state of knowledge, EU scholars show preferences that differ from those of US scholars. While EU scholars clearly tend to favor a process-oriented research design under this condition, US scholars are divided between choosing a confirmatory or process-oriented design and a relevant proportion also chooses an exploratory design.

A.4: Manipulation check

As a manipulation check, we asked respondents the following question:

“Do you agree with the following statement? Empirical studies about the causes-of effects (i.e., What causes Y?) are only useful to analyze new phenomena or research topics that have received little attention by previous research. (Yes/No).”

This question was intended to explore the meaning of the treatment, as it was perceived by respondents. We expected that the survey experiment would make respondents aware of the relationship between the state of knowledge and goals of inference and that, correspondingly, many respondents would agree with the statement. In particular, we expected that respondents for whom the experimental condition matches the context described in the statement of the manipulation check (i.e., analyze new phenomena or research topics that have received little attention by previous research) to be more likely to agree with the statement. However, only a very few respondents (i.e., 60 out of 901) agreed with this statement. In hindsight, we believe the wording of the manipulation check might have been too deterministic (“... are only useful...”) for some researchers to express agreement with it. Moreover, we did not specify our expectations about the outcome of the manipulation check in detail in the preanalysis plan. Accordingly, the following analyses should be considered exploratory.

Despite the low level of support for the statement among respondents in general, we analyzed the effect of the experimental treatment on the outcome of the manipulation check. Figure A6 describes the results of a logistic regression model with agreement to the manipulation check question as binary outcome variable. As shown there, our experimental treatment did not affect the probability that respondents agreed with the statement. Moreover, method preferences also appear to be unrelated to the response to the manipulation check statement.

Figure A6: Effect of experimental treatment and method preferences on manipulation check

To address concerns about failed manipulation, we conduct two additional analysis that utilize the manipulation check variable. First, we replicate our main analysis while adding the manipulation check question as an additional covariate to the multinomial logit model. The results are described in Figure A7.

Figure A7: Treatment effects when manipulation check is included as covariate

Figure A7 shows that including the manipulation check as a covariate does not seem to affect the size and statistical significance of the estimated treatment effects. The results are substantially the same as those reported in the main text.

Second, we also conducted a subgroup analysis for the effect of the state of knowledge manipulation on goals of inference, distinguishing between those respondents that agree and those that disagree with the statement of the manipulation check. Empirically, we do not find substantial differences regarding the direction and size of the treatment effect of the experimental manipulation between researchers agreeing and researchers disagreeing with the statement of the manipulation check. Figure A8 describes the results of interaction models, wherein the experimental treatment is interacted with a binary variable, indicating agreement with the manipulation check question. The treatment effect is very similar for scholars that agree and scholars that disagree with the manipulation check statement.

Figure A8: Treatment effect interaction with manipulation check

Altogether, we conclude that the low level of agreement with the manipulation check appears to be not a problem for the interpretation of the experimental treatment effect.

A.5: Alternative coding of research culture

When coding the method preferences of respondents, we encountered participants who responded that they have a small number of cases and use large-N methods, or the other way around. This concerns 28 participants. We decided to code them as ‘missing’. The small-N-cases/large-N methods combination is contradictory. The large-N cases/small-N-methods combination could be possible in practice (Goertz 2017, chapter 7), but it is an exceptional combination that, in our view, no researcher uses regularly in empirical research.

Since we did not pre-register this coding decision for research cultures, we conducted a sensitivity analysis that included these participants in the empirical analysis and coded them as mixed-methods researchers. The results for the main effects of the experimental treatment and method preferences are reported in Figure A9. In Figures A10 and A11, we replicate the analysis of the

interaction between the experimental treatment and research cultures, with the alternative coding procedure.

Figure A9: Marginal effects with alternative coding procedure

Figure A10: Effect of experimental treatment across research cultures with alternative coding

Figure A11: Probability of choosing a specific goal of inference across research cultures and treatment conditions with alternative coding

Finally, Figures A12 and A13 report the results for the replication of the interaction between the experimental treatment and the continent of scholars using the alternative coding procedure. Figures A9 to A13 show that the estimated main and interaction do not differ substantially from the original estimates. All results are essentially the same with regard to effect sizes and statistical significance.

Figure A12: Effect of experimental treatment across continents with alternative coding procedure

Figure A13: Probability of choosing a specific goal of inference across continents and treatment conditions with alternative coding procedure

A6: Distribution of method preferences across continents

Table A16 summarizes the distribution of methods preferences in the EU and US. Given that methods training at highly ranked US departments is primarily quantitative, it was to be expected that we see a somewhat higher share of self-identified quantitative researchers in the US and a higher share of qualitative scholars in Europe (Moses, Rihoux, and Kittel 2005; Emmons and Moravcsik 2020). We were a bit surprised that a majority of researchers in Europe and the US self-identify as mixed-methods researchers. We see this as a positive sign for methodological pluralism that the category with the highest share refers to researchers that use both types of methods.

Table A16: Distribution of method preferences in the US and EU

Culture	Continent		
	EU	US	Total
Qualitative	114 (26.21%)	36 (7.73%)	150 (16.65%)
Quantitative	134 (30.80%)	175 (37.55%)	309 (34.30%)
Mixed-method	187 (42.99%)	255 (54.72%)	442 (49.06%)
Total	435 (100%)	466 (100%)	901 (100%)

Raw frequencies with percentage shares in parentheses

A.7: Deviations from the preanalysis plan

Hypothesis 3 (H3) originally was formulated as follows:

H3: Researchers are not influenced by the maturity of the state of the art for a research topic, but instead specify their goals of inference based on their predetermined research cultures.

We later decided to drop “... are not influenced by the maturity of the state of the art for a research topic, but instead ...” from the hypothesis. We derive the hypothesis from the “A Tale of Two Cultures” argument that researchers adopt the research approach based on their academic socialization (Goertz and Mahoney, 2012, chapter 1). In this perspective on the choice of the approach, it is not claimed that the state of research does *not* matter, which is what the part of the hypothesis that we dropped insinuates. For this reason, we reformulated the hypothesis such that it correctly reflects two-cultures argument.

References in Appendix

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